

Mechanical Behavior of Silicon Carbide Whisker Reinforced Aluminum Alloys

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ABSTRACT

Aluminum alloys reinforced with silicon carbide whiskers produced from low cost rice hulls represent a new class of metal matrix composites. The Materials Division of Exxon Enterprises is developing an isotropically reinforced family of these composites, identified as SXATM alloys, using conventional metal-working technology. Extruded, forged and flat stock have been produced and evaluated. Mechanical characteristics of these SXATM alloys, present an exciting opportunity for reducing weight and extending performance beyond the limits of conventional alloys. Composites containing 2000-, 6000-, and 7000- series aluminum alloys as the matrix show improvements in strength, stiffness, fatigue and creep of fifty to one-hundred percent over corresponding unreinforced alloys. Experimental data for elastic properties (modulus, expansivity, etc.) shows excellent agreement with composite theory.

INTRODUCTION

Fabrication of silicon carbide whisker reinforced metal matrix composites on near-conventional metal-working equipment provides a unique opportunity for the use of these materials in complex structural applications without the restraint of large capital investments by the customer. This subtle benefit was recognized by Parratt (1, 2) during his early developments over fifteen years ago. An excellent review (3) recently emphasized the formability of the silicon carbide whisker reinforced composites and demonstrated the performance benefits achievable. In addition to the fabrication advantage, the success of this new class of composites is clearly dependent on the development and availability of relatively low-cost whiskers (4) and the reproducible production of metal matrix composite billets for the subsequent fabrication of mill shapes such as extrusions, sheets, plates and forgings.

The Materials Division of Exxon Enterprises has developed both silicon carbide whiskers, using the pyrolysis of rice hulls, and the fabrication of a new class of metal matrix composites which are near-isotropically reinforced (identified as SXATM alloys). Current mechanical properties provide a cost effective alternative and, through the selection of the matrix alloy, whisker concentration, and reinforcement morphology, the designer can adjust the

properties to the application. Considerable work remains before the optimum potential of the SXA™ alloys will be realized and, therefore, it is the objective of the following discussion to describe a range of current mechanical properties to stimulate more extensive investigations by the composite community.

EXPERIMENTAL FABRICATION

Submicron silicon carbide whisker reinforcements produced from a low-cost raw material, rice hulls, are mixed with inert atomized aluminum alloy powders and vacuum, liquid-phase compacted as schematically shown in Figure 1. Homogenized billets are converted into mill shapes using conventional metal-working procedures. Commercial extrusion equipment is used to produce rods, tubes, plate-bar and shaped sections. In cooperation with commercial fabricators, forgings, plate, sheet and formed shapes are produced on near-standard tooling. (3)

FIGURE 1. FABRICATION OF SILICON CARBIDE WHISKERS AND REINFORCED METAL COMPOSITES

Using the fabrication method described, commercial aluminum alloys such as 1100, 2024, 5083 and 7075 are fabricated with silicon carbide contents ranging from five (5) to thirty (30) volume percent. Submicron silicon carbide powder is also incorporated as a reinforcement for selected applications. Experimental quantities of advanced aluminum alloys such as X7090, X7091 and aluminum-lithium are produced. Billet sizes up to twelve-inch diameter and one hundred eighty pounds are pressed and converted on commercial equipment.

DISCUSSION OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Theoretical values for the elastic modulus of silicon carbide reinforced aluminum was analyzed by Riggs (5) as a function of the reinforcement concentration, morphology, and arrangement. Figure 2 presents these results. Figure 3 compares the theoretical values for unidirectional composites of several reinforcement length-to-diameter (L/d) ratios with experimental data determined for isotropically arranged whisker reinforced aluminum composites. After fabrication the whiskers were solvent extracted and the L/d determined to be between five (5) and ten (10). These experimental data are in good agreement with the theory and slightly above the values predicted for an isotropic array. This seems to indicate that either the whiskers have aligned somewhat during fabrication or that the constituent properties for the silicon carbide whiskers are greater than assumed (modulus for silicon carbide assumed to be 70 million psi). Recently, data (6, 7) on particulate reinforced aluminum were compared with whisker composites and confirm the value of the whisker L/d. To further demonstrate this, a series of silicon carbide reinforced composites were fabricated maintaining a constant volume percent of silicon carbide but varying the ratio of whiskers to particulates in each composite. Therefore, composites ranging from 20 volume percent particulate reinforcement to 20 volume percent whisker reinforcement were fabricated and evaluated. The results for these composites are presented in Figure 4 for the elastic modulus and elongation and in Figure 5 for the ultimate and yield strengths. It is apparent from these results that the stiffness and strengths increase as the fraction of whisker reinforcement increases. This is consistent with theory and comparable experimental results.

FIGURE 2. EFFECT OF SIC CONCENTRATION OF EFFECTIVE MODULUS

FIGURE 3. EFFECTIVE MODULUS VERSUS CONCENTRATION OF SILICON CARBIDE WHISKERS

FIGURE 4. EFFECT OF WHISKER/PARTICULATE RATIO ON MODULUS OF ELASTICITY AND ELONGATION OF 6061-T6 ALUMINUM/SiC COMPOSITE

FIGURE 5. EFFECT OF SILICON CARBIDE WHISKER/PARTICULATE RATIO ON STRENGTH OF 6061-T6 ALUMINUM/SiC COMPOSITE

FIGURE 6. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SiC WHISKER REINFORCED 6061 ALUMINUM ALLOY

Analysis of the strengthening mechanisms that operate in a composite reinforced with discontinuous silicon carbide show that the composite strength is the sum of the basic matrix strength plus the contribution due to the reinforcement. For reinforcements which have an L/d greater than the critical L/d (estimated to be about 10 for silicon carbide in an aluminum alloy) and which are well bonded to the matrix, this is the critical parameter for strengthening. For particles (L/d of 1) the mechanism is more likely dispersion strengthening of the matrix, and is inversely proportional to the interparticle spacing and hence the particle size. It is therefore apparent that decreasing the particle size or increasing the number of small particles is the primary route to strengthening by this method. This is well documented in the metallurgical literature. Due to the complex nature of strength predictions, emphasis has been placed on generating experimental results. Figure 6 shows the effect of silicon carbide whisker concentrations from five (5) to twenty-five (25) percent on strength, stiffness and ductility. Compared to the unreinforced aluminum alloy, the elastic modulus is increased by nearly a factor of two (2) and the ultimate strength for this alloy is improved from 45 to 80 thousand pounds per square inch. Elongations up to five (5) percent can be realized for reinforcement concentrations of five (5) percent. These data show the type property adjustments available to the materials designer. Similar data are available for other alloy systems and moduli up to twenty-five (25) million pounds per square inch and ultimate tensile strengths in excess of one hundred (100) thousand pounds per square inch have been attained.

Creep data for a whisker reinforced 2024 aluminum alloy are presented in Figure 7. These data are chosen to demonstrate the influence of the reinforcements on elevated temperature performance. For this alloy, the creep resistance is improved by approximately one hundred percent at a temperature of 300°C. Short term, high temperature test results show a similar trend for the SXA™ alloys, and the useful continuous temperature limit is increased by about one hundred (100) degrees centigrade.

FIGURE 7. CREEP BEHAVIOR OF SiC WHISKER REINFORCED 2024 ALUMINUM ALLOY

Whisker damage during fabrication has been a major concern. Figure 8 presents metallographic data after sheet rolling and extrusion. Definitely, the whiskers have been reduced in length, but a significant fraction of the whiskers retained an L/d in excess of five (5). The uniformity of whisker distribution is observed for both fabrication methods, and the whisker alignment appears to be more isotropic in the plane of the sheet for the rolled product.

CONCLUSION

The newly developed class of silicon carbide whisker, isotropically reinforced aluminum alloy composites (SXATM) present an opportunity to reduce weight, increase performance and remain cost effective. The elastic behavior of the SXATM composites are consistent with composite theory and the strength, creep and elevated temperature behavior exceed that available from conventional aluminum alloys. The advantages of whisker morphology relative to particles for increasing the stiffness of these composites are demonstrated experimentally. The mechanisms for strengthening appear to be generally defined, and experimental results clearly indicate the potential for these composites.

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WHISKER APPEARANCE IN EXTRUDED 0.5 INCH x 5 INCH FLAT
ETCHED 1200X

WHISKER APPEARANCE IN SHEET ROLLED FROM EXTRUDED FLAT
ETCHED ROLLING PLANE VIEW 1200X

FIGURE 8. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS OF FABRICATED SiC
WHISKER REINFORCED 6061 ALUMINUM ALLOY